

THE IMPACT OF PERIODONTAL DISEASE ON THE OCCURRENCE OF VARIOUS TYPES OF SECONDARY DEFORMATION AND THEIR PREVALENCE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of our study was to identify and spread species secondary deformation of the dentition, the cause of which was periodontal disease. We examined 519 patients. survey results show that the most common various types of compatible deformations and fan-shaped divergence teeth. Of the compatible ones, the fan-shaped discrepancy with inclination, rotation and position of teeth in different variants. Recently, the prevalence of secondary deformity has sharply increased. In people over 40, it is more common than caries. Aim of our study was to establish the prevalence of secondary deformities of the dentition in periodontal diseases. For implementation of the assigned task for 12 months, we examined all patients who came to the clinic. It was found that the prevalence of secondary deformations of the dentition that have arisen due to periodontal disease, is 10.98%, the largest number falls on the age of 51 to 60 years, of which 75.44% - women.

Keywords: types of secondary deformation of dental rows, prevalence, periodontium.

The incidence of dentoalveolar deformities still attracts attention of many researchers [3.4.7]. There are data in the literature on the prevalence of pathology is significantly different from each other, which due not only to the timing of observations, but also to many other physiological and social factors[1.5.8]. Certain interventions for the extraction of individual teeth are accompanied by persistent morphofunctional disorders in the dentition system, which are characterized by the displacement of individual teeth in different directions, atrophic or hypertrophic processes of bone tissues of the alveolar processes [2]. Violations of the bone structure were noted only in the area of extracted teeth, but also in the area of their antagonists and even in areas of intact teeth on the opposite side of the jaw, which puts the problem of orthopedic treatment of this pathology in the category relevant[6]. The most important feature of the dento-jaw system is that when chewing and swallowing at the time of closure of the dentition the periodontium of each tooth perceives the force load, which under normal conditions is depreciated, is transformed and transmitted to the bone tissues of the jaws, temporomandibular joint and skull[9]. As a result periodontal weakening normal occlusal loading begins to exceed the tolerance of its structure and transformed from a stimulating factor into a traumatic. Traumatic occlusion occurs playing a leading role in the future secondary deformations [10]

The purpose of our study is to establish the diversity of species secondary deformation of the dentition and their prevalence in periodontal diseases.

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHODS

The study consisted of a patient survey and clarification of questions regarding the development of this disease. Accounting the following data were subject: age, profession, presence of harmful habits, accompanying a disease with a chronic course, hereditary burden, allergic history, hygienic status (teeth cleaning, regularity, used pastes, technique teeth cleaning and gum massage). Noted when the first signs appeared periodontal disease, with which the patient associates its occurrence, Have you consulted a doctor before, for help, by what methods was carried out the treatment, its effectiveness.

When collecting an anamnesis of the disease, of particular interest to us were questions about prescription, the occurrence of deformations of the dentition, developed due to a pathological process in the periodontium. When examining a face paid attention to aesthetic violations, lowering the height lower third of the face, the severity of nasolabial and chin folds. When examining the oral cavity, special attention was paid to identifying deformities of the dentition resulting from periodontal disease. Find out when the patient first noticed the changed position of the teeth in the dentition, how it developed deformation. The presence of knots blocking the movements of the lower jaws, determined the presence of defects in the dentition, crowns of teeth,

their condition. The nature of the closure of the dentition, the type of bite were noted.

RESULTS

During the survey period, 519 people were examined.

During the examination, a group of individuals was identified, deformations of the dentition in developed as a result of periodontal disease. In this the group did not include persons with anomalies in the develop-

ment of the dento-jaw system and deformities of another etiology. It was found that out of 519 examined, 57 a person had secondary deformations of the dentition associated with course of periodontal disease, which accounted for 10.98% of the total the number of those examined. The age of the examined patients was from 19 to 70 years. The distribution of persons with secondary deformations of the dentition according to age and sex are presented in the table.

	age										total	
	19-30		31-40		41-50		51-60		61-70		№	%
	№	%	№	%	№	%	№	%	№	%		
man			1	1,75	5	8,77	7	12,28	1	1,75	14	24,56
woman	1	1,75	2	3,5	18	31,58	19	33,33	3	5,26	43	75,44
total	1	1,75	3	5,25	23	40,35	26	45,61	4	7,01	57	100%

The data presented in the table indicate that secondary deformities of the dentition, developed as a result of periodontal disease, occur more frequently in women than in men. Out of 57 persons with secondary deformities of the dentition, 43 (75.44%) - women and 14 (24.56%) - men. When distributed by age groups, the largest number falls on the age of 51 to 60 years - 26 (49.05%) people, of which 19 (33.33%) - women and 7 (12.28%) - men, from 41 to 50 years old - 23 (40.35%) persons, of which 18 (31.57%) are women and 5 (8.770%) are men. Minor number of people in the age group from 19 to 30 years and from 31 to 40 years due to the fact that the development of pathological pro-

cesses is on the initial stage and secondary deformations have not yet been discovered. sharp reduction in the number of secondary deformations of the dentition in the age group from 61 to 70 years can be explained by the fact that patients in this group complex treatment of the disease was repeatedly carried out, which necessarily included orthopedic, aimed at eliminating deformities and restoration of missing teeth.

The secondary deformations of the dentition found by us systematized, analyzed and distributed according to types.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION
as follows (Table 1)

Table 1

Types of secondary deformations of the dentition resulting from diseases periodontal

Type of deformation	man		woman		total	
	№	%	№	%	№	%
fan-shaped divergence of teeth	1	1,75	2	3,5	3	5,25
Crowding of teeth	-		1	1,75	1	1,75
tilt of the teeth	2	3,50	3	5,3	5	8,8
Diastema trema	1	1,75	1	1,75	2	3,5
rotation of the tooth around the axis	1	1,75	2	3,5	3	5,25
supraocclusion	3	5,25	3	5,25	6	10,5
infraocclusion	1	1,75	1	1,75	2	3,5
Total deformation	3	5,3	32	56,14	35	61,45
	12	21,05	45	78,95	57	100

The data presented in Table 1 indicate that the most common secondary deformations of the dentition that have arisen due to periodontal disease, are compatible. Them found in 35 people out of 57, which is 61.45%, in males - 3 (5.3%), female - 32 (56.14%). 3 (5.25%) people had fan-shaped divergence of teeth, of which 1 (1.750%) men and 2 (3.50%) women. 5 (8.8%) people had tooth tilt, of which 2 (3.50%) men and 3 (5.25%) women.

Rotation of teeth around its axis was less common in 3 (5.25%) people, 1 (1.75%) of which a man and 2

(3.50%) women. In 2 (3.5%) patients, 1 (1.75%) of which was a woman and 1 (1.75%) a man developed a diastema and three. Also, in 6 (10.5%) people, supra and infraocclusions were detected, of which 3 (5.25%) women and 3 (5.25%) people, and 2 (3.5%) people, of which 1 (1.75%) man and 1 (1.75%) women noted corpus tooth movement. 1 (1.50%) of the individual had crowded teeth. Thus, the most frequent types of deformations of the dentition are compatible. Therefore, we believe it is expedient to consider and analyze them (Table 2).

Table 2

Total deformations of the dentition due to diseases periodontal.

types of deformation	man		woman		total	
	№	%	№	%	№	%
fan-shaped discrepancy and inclination of teeth	1	1.75	5	8,77	6	10,52
fan-shaped discrepancy and rotation of teeth			1	1,75	1	1,75
Fan-shaped discrepancy and supra-occlusion	1	1.75	4	7	5	8.75
Fan-shaped discrepancy and infra-occlusion	-	-	1	1,75	1	1,75
Fan-shaped discrepancy with inclination and rotation of teeth	1	1.75	3	5,26	4	7,01
Fan-shaped divergence with rotation and supra-occlusion	1	1.75	3	5,26	4	7,01
Fan-shaped divergence with tilt and infraocclusion	-	-	2	3,5	2	3,5
Fan-shaped divergence with rotation and infraocclusion	-	-	3	5,26	3	5,26
crowding of teeth with dystema and trema	-	-	2	3,5	2	3,5
Crowding with carcass movement of teeth	-	-	1	1,75	1	1,75
Crowding with tilted teeth	2	3.50	3	5,26	5	8,76
Crowding will move the area of the dentition		-				
Tilted teeth with rotation	2	3.50	3	5,26	5	8,76
Tilt teeth with body movement	-	-	3	5,26	3	5,26
Tilt teeth with supraocclusion or infraocclusion	2	3.50	2	3,5	4	7,01
Diastema, trema and body movement of teeth	1	1.75	3	5,26	4	7,01
Teeth rotation with supra and infraocclusions	-	-	4	7.0	4	7.0
Supra and infraocclusions of detached teeth	1	1.75	2	3,5	3	5,25
	12	21.00	45	79	57	100

From the material presented in Table 2, it can be noted that the most often there is a combination of fan-shaped divergence of teeth with other deformations. We observed this pathology in 19 (33.33%) cases, it was in 3 (5.25%) men and 16 (28.07%) women. Tilt of teeth with suproclulsion or infraocclusion was in 4 (7.0%) people, of which 2 (3.5%) men and 2 (3.5%) women. Diastema, tremaya in combination with the body movement of the teeth was observed in 4 (7.0%) people - 1 (1.75%) male and 3 (5.25%) female. crowding of teeth in combination with other deformities in 3 (5.25) women.

References

1. Alimsky A. B. Age-related changes in the dentition systems / A.B. Alimsky // Russian Dental journal: Scientific and practical journal. — M.: Medicine, 2004 - No. 4 - P.26-29
2. Bezrukova I.V. Aggressive forms periodontitis./I.V. Buzrukova, A.I. Grudianov LLC Medical news agency. 2002
3. Gavrilov E.I. Deformations of the dentition / Gavrilov E.I. – M.: - "Medicine", 1984 - P. 13-38
4. Gavrilov E.I. Atlas of deformations of the dentition. / Gavrilov E. I., Bolshakov G.V. - Publishing House of Saratov University, 1992 - P. 4 -134
5. Zhulev E. N. Clinic, diagnostics and orthopedic treatment periodontal diseases. / Zhulev E. N. - Nizh. Novgorod, NGMA, - 2003 - 320 p
6. Zolotoreva Yu.B., Guseva I.E. Influence of occlusal disorders on the course inflammatory process in periodontal tissues. Dentistry 2001, No. 4 p.21-24
7. Kovalenko A.F., Varava G.M. The mechanism of formation of dentoalveolar deformities after partial loss of teeth. Dentistry 2003 №5 p.42-44
8. Mashchenko I. S. Biomechanical modeling of bearing capacity tooth with changes in periodontal tissues / I. S. Mashchenko, O. V. Gromov, A. N. Chuiko // Modern dentistry. - No. 1 (21). – 2003
9. Onopa E.N. Prevalence of dentition deformities in patients with partial absence of teeth with varying degrees abrasion. Modern problems of science and education. 2012, No. 4 URL: <https://science-education.ru/ru/article/view?id=6469> (date of access: 03/05/2022).
10. Ponomareva V. A. Mechanisms of development and ways to eliminate dentoalveolar deformities / Ponomareva V. A. - M., "Medicine", 1974 – 110 s.